

ON THE EMERGENCE OF PSYCHOLINGUISTICS, ITS CURRENT SIGNIFICANCE AND BENEFITS FOR FUTURE GENERATIONS

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Abstract: *The object and subject of psycholinguistics. Specific features of psycholinguistics: the human factor, the situational factor, the principle of experiment. Conceptual-terminological apparatus. Psycholinguistics as a psychological science. Psycholinguistics and Linguistics. Individuality and communication. The Interrelationship of Psycholinguistics with Other Disciplines.*

Keywords: *Psychology, Psycholinguistics, Psychoanalysis, Individual, Communication, Speech, Speech Ontogeny.*

О ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИИ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИКИ, ЕЕ СОВРЕМЕННОМ ЗНАЧЕНИИ И ПОЛЬЗЕ ДЛЯ БУДУЩИХ ПОКОЛЕНИЙ

Аннотация: *Объект и предмет психолингвистики. Особенности психолингвистики: человеческий фактор, ситуативный фактор, принцип эксперимента. Понятийно-терминологический аппарат. Психолингвистика как психологическая наука. Психолингвистика и лингвистика. Индивидуальность и общение. Взаимосвязь психолингвистики с другими дисциплинами.*

Ключевые слова: *психология, психолингвистика, психоанализ, личность, общение, речь, онтогенез речи.*

INTRODUCTION

Psycholinguistics is the study of the formation of speech, as well as the processes of speech perception and formation in the context of their interaction with the language system; arose from the synthesis of psychology and linguistics. P. develops a model of human speech activity and psychophysiological speech formation and examines them through psychological experiments. P., who is close to linguistics in the source of his research, is close to psychology in his research methods. It uses interrelated experiments, such as "semantic differential" and other experimental methods. P. a number of practical issues [mother tongue, especially foreign language teaching; issues of speech education and speech therapy for preschool children; clinic of diseases of speech centers in the brain; speech problems (especially in the media and advocacy); forensic psychology and criminology (eg, identification of people according to the nature of their speech); It arose in the 1960s due to the need for machine translation and the theoretical explanation of the problems of accessing speech information to computers and so on. "P." The term was coined by American scholars in the mid-1960s. Although some work has been done in Uzbekistan in this area, genuine psycholinguistic research is only just beginning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The object and subject of psycholinguistics. Specific features of psycholinguistics: the human factor, the situational factor, the principle of experiment. Conceptual-terminological apparatus. Psycholinguistics as a psychological science. Psycholinguistics and Linguistics. Individuality and communication. The Interrelationship of Psycholinguistics with Other Disciplines.

Psychological and linguistic sources of psycholinguistics. Early psycholinguistic ideas. The antinomy of V. von Humboldt. The theory of "young grammarians": individual psychology.

The Crisis of the Theory of Young Grammarians. The formation of psycholinguistics as an independent science. LS Vygotsky is one of the founders of psycholinguistics. The doctrine of internal speech.

Psycholinguistics - 54. Charles Osgood's model of communication. A linguistic approach to human communication. An approach to human communication from psychology. Approach to human communication from information theory. Scheme of human communication. Behaviorism, non-behaviorism. Stimulus (S) and reaction (R). Associative relations.

RESULTS

J. Miller and N. Chomsky Transformation School

Transformation-generative grammar of Noam Chomsky. The first variant of the transformational model, its general structure and features. The importance of the transformational model in placing natural language expressions in automatic circuits. The second variant of the transformational model. The concepts of "inner" structure and "external" structure. N. Chomsky's concepts of competence (linguistic ability) and performance (linguistic activity). The main features of the teachings of George Miller. J. Miller's communication model.

Speech ontogenesis

The language of animals in nature. Mowgli children. Views on language acquisition (speech ontogenesis). Language skills. The relationship between language knowledge and language use. Features of children's speech. Formation of protosemantic characters in children's speech. The semantic stage in children's speech. Children's vocabulary skills. The importance of adult speech in the formation of children's speech. That is one of the main aspects of socialization in the formation of children's speech and intellectual activity. Mistakes in children's speech.

Speech activity and its types. The concept of "speech activity". The structure of speech activity. Psychological mechanism of speech activity. Types of speech activities. Verbal and nonverbal thinking. Subjective (psychological) essence of speech activity. Functions of language and speech in speech activity.

Speech creation. Psycholinguistic interpretation of speech creation. Speech is an activity. Leading and auxiliary types of activities. L.S.Vigotskiy model. Contemplation and speech. Systematic structure of consciousness. From thought to meaning, from meaning to word. Inner word. A.R.Luria model. Dynamic scheme of expression. Three stages in the creation of speech. 1. Semantic stage. The theme and rhyme of the text. 2. Internal speech. 3. Formation of common speech expressions. A.A. Leontev model. Programming the grammatical-semantic aspects of expression. Grammatical realization of expressions and word choice. Motor programming of syntagms.

Speech comprehension. Accept the text (understand the text). Extract text content. Verbal or physical response. Consider the application. Incompatibility of message-1 with message-2. Principles of efficiency, economy and reliability in creating and understanding text.

DISCUSSION

Psycholinguistic study of the text

The role of language tools in revealing the linguistic essence of text. The role of language and thinking in the psycholinguistic analysis of the text. That the text is a form of communication act. The concepts of "author", "text" and "recipient". There are three main levels of speech reception.

Psycholinguistic research methods. Experimental methods. Types of experiments. Experimental work in the field of phonetics, semantics. Paradigmatic and syntagmatic forms of

association. Associative experiment and its types. Free associative experiment. Oriented associative experiment. Chain associative experiment. Creating dictionaries of associative norms. Experimental study of words and word groups. Experimental study of speech and text. Experiments on the periphrasis of transformational trends in psycholinguistics. Advantages of the method of "key words" in the study of the semantic structure of the text.

Pathopsycholinguistics. Speech pathology and its study on the basis of psycholinguistic methods. The main manifestations of speech pathology. History of the study of aphasia. Aphasia and its types. Total aphasia. Partial aphasia. Motor aphasia. Sensory aphasia. Acoustic aphasia. Semantic aphasia. Telegraph method. Alalia and her views. Sensor alaliya. Motor alaliya. Sensomotor alalia. Physiological centers of speech. Broka Center. Vernike zone. Features of speech organization in schizophrenia.

Ethnopsycholinguistics. Language and culture. National and cultural features of the word. National-cultural features of nonverbal speech. Lacunas. Verbal communication. Bilingualism and its types. Mistakes in learning a foreign language. Speech of foreigners. Cultural shock. Linguistic shock. Intercultural communication.

CONCLUSIONS

The Interrelationship of Psycholinguistics with Other Disciplines.

Psychological and linguistic sources of psycholinguistics. Early psycholinguistic ideas. The antinomy of V. von Humboldt. The theory of "young grammarians": individual psychology. The Crisis of the Theory of Young Grammarians. The formation of psycholinguistics as an independent science. LS Vygotsky is one of the founders of psycholinguistics. The doctrine of internal speech.

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